

Residue properties

1481862

a. Absolute deviation from mean Chi-1 value (excl. Pro)

b. Absolute deviation from mean of omega torsion

c. C-alpha chirality: abs. deviation of zeta torsion

Highlighted residues are those that deviate by more than 2.0 st. devs. from ideal

d. Secondary structure & estimated accessibility

e. Sequence & Ramachandran regions

f. Max. deviation (see listing)

g. G-factors

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c = cis-peptide

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